

DEVELOPMENT PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF NAMANGAN CITY

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola hududlarning oʻz imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda ularning geourbanistik salohiyatini oshirish, aholining ijtimoiy-turmush darajasini yanada yaxshilash, hududda mavjud kamchiliklarni bartaraf etishga qaratilgan va Namangan shahri misolida yoritib berilgan. Ayrim muammo va kamchiliklarga tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Geourbanistika, aglomeratsiya, hududiy birlik, migratsiya, ijtimoiy turmush darajasi, aholi bandligi, aholi zichligi, mayatniksimon migratsiya, investitsiya.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ГОРОДА НАМАНГАН

АННОТАЦИЯ

данная статья направлена на повышение геоурбанистического потенциала регионов исходя из их возможностей; дальнейшее улучшение социально-жизненного уровня населения; устранение имеющихся на территории недостатков и освещена на примере города Наманган. Даны рекомендации по некоторым проблемам и недостаткам.

Ключевые слова: Геоурбанистика, агломерация, уровень жизни населения, территориальная единица, занятность населения, плотность населения, маятниковая миграция, инвестиции.

PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT OPPORTUNITIES OF NAMANGAN CITY

ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at increasing the geourbanistic potential of the regions due to their capabilities, further improving the social and living standards of the population, shortcomings in the territory, and is highlighted by the example of the city of Namangan. Recommendations were made to some problems and shortcomings.

Key words: Geourbanistics, agglomeration, the standard of living the population, population density, population employment, pendulum migration, investments.

According to the historical and cultural significance of the city network of Uzbekistan after Tashkent, although Samarkand occupies the second place, according to the rules of urban studies is considered demographic Namangan. It is the largest city in the Fergana Valley, the Regional Center. It has more than 600 thousand inhabitants, 22 percent of the population of the region is embodied. The geographical location of the city is also convenient, it is located in the foothills of Adir, in the conical spread of Namangansoy, in the foothills of Sirdarya. The southern part is adjacent to the broad agricultural district, and the northern part to the livestock District of Adir. The passage of the railway and cross-country highway from the northern part will further facilitate the transport-geographic location. The city was founded in the XVI century. During the period of Russian composition (1880-90), the first cotton-cleaning and oil-fat-drying enterprises were formed. Since then, the industry. In 1950-ies, the city became the main center of the Republic's economy and food industry, with 94 percent of its industry accounted for the same area, separated from other cities⁹⁸. Cotton fiber, silk, oil and oil products of industrial enterprises were exported not only to the Republic, but also to the Union. In the pre-Independence period, the city for many years functioned as the largest light industry center of the Fergana Valley.

The socio-political changes that took place after independence, the collapse of large industrial enterprises, the stagnation of relation with the Allied republics, the city was in a monophonic direction and became a depressive city as a result of the disruption of the activities of the city-forming branches.

In the following years of independence, work was carried out to restore the city, diversify the industry. „Silk Road”, „Nestle”, „Asnam Tekstil”s were established, currently the number of joint ventures 36 still light in the composition of industries and

⁹⁸ Смирнов Н. Города Ферганской долины. - Т., 1957. 131-бет.

food industrial enterprises constitute the majority. Businesses lying without work are numerous.

The population of the city is growing faster than in other cities. This situation is primarily on account of the city and its environs, while still on account of the fact that the city is tilting towards the periphery. In the next 8 years, the population of the city increased to 60 thousand, that is, by 10 percent. From 2000 to the present day, according to the pace of population growth, the Republic is the leader among cities. Among the administrative units of the region, it can also be seen that it is growing

Cities and districts	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
By region	2298	2316	2458,7	2054,2	2554,2	2603,4	2652,4	2699,5	2752,7
Namangan sh	449,2	452,8	468,0	475.7	484.9	493.3	490.2	600.2	612.2
Mingbuloq	100.3	101.1	109.9	111.9	114.2	116.4	118.5	120.6	123.1
Kosonsoy	164.3	105.8	130.9	184.9	188.4	192.1	195.9	199.7	203.9
Namangan	187.7	189.5	207.7	212.0	216.8	221.6	176.3	170.8	174.6
Norin	33.1	134.0	144.6	147.1	149.9	152.4	154.9	157.4	160.3
Pop	179.1	180.5	193.1	196.8	200.5	204.2	207.9	211.3	215.0
To'raqo'rg'on	183.2	184.5	194.7	198.5	203.0	207.6	212.0	216.2	220.6
Uychi	192.5	194.0	203.0	207.1	211.9	216.4	199.5	203.4	207.7
Uchqo'rg'on	144.6	145.6	151.4	153.9	156.8	159.6	162.4	165.2	168.2
Chortoq	163.3	164.5	175.7	178.9	182.4	186.0	187.3	190.9	194.6
Chust	221.4	223.1	233.5	237.6	242.0	246.7	251.0	254.9	259.7
Yangiqo'rg'on	197.1	180.4	196.2	199.7	203.4	207.1	205.4	208.8	212.8

rapidly (table). Along with this, a large number of flights from the nearest districts to the city of the population are also observed. And this puts a lot of pressure on the city

Dynamics of population of Namangan region and Namangan city(table-1)

This larger the cities, the higher its power should also be. In this respect, it has the capacity to capture 50-60km of areas into its sphere of influence. However, the slowness of the city's industrial potential, the low bandwidth, the lack of improvement in its social infrastructure undermine the city's position and importance. The city basically performs and administrative function, in this respect, although managing districts, the power of influence on the population settlements of other nearby regional and army States is not felt.

The social infrastructure of the city Namangan, the state of roads, architecture-construction, engineering-technical condition can not meet the growing population requirements. As a result, favorable condition for the normal life of the existing population are increasingly. Dozens of such examples can be cited: traffic jams in the hours of the road, the inability to fully meet the communal needs of Alisher Navoi Street, Non-Residential, the increase in the capacity of clean drinking water, electricity,

sewerage atizimi, educational and health institutions. Especially clean drinking water in the city is a big problem. In the central regions such as buds, sardines, Pahlavon, Lola, there is observed such a hola thicket. Clean drinking water to the city comes from the underground water reserve of the Naryn River. The reservoir is located near the territory of Jiydakapa. During the precipitation of the year, the water becomes turbid and naughty for the consumption of the population.

There is such a law that the more the population, the less the conditions and culture of the city will be. The infrastructure of the city, the living conditions of the population, the status of architectural objects show that false urbanization. At present, the most dense and most “Chaotic” city of the region is Namangan. Although, in general, there is no ring-shaped transport route, even if there are large markets in the city. Especially “Sardoba”, “Chorsu” market is very limited to navigation around. The city must first of all give people the spirit to live in a settlement. “City” is called, but if coal for heating the house in the winter is left, and water for drinking in the summer is transported, can it fit city? In order to prevent these issues, the Twenty-Third Plenary Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan considered the issues of changing the borders of Namangan city, Turakurgan, Kosonsoy, Namangan District of Namangan region, as well as Kurgantepa District of Khanabad city of Andijan region. According to him, the central streets of the city of Namangan and the main part of the area of Kosonsoy, Namangan, Yangikurgan districts were added to the territory of the city with an area of 1 thousand 39 at the point of housing provision of the people who feel into the reconstruction⁹⁹. This, in turn, raises a number of problems in the provision of municipal services, the development of Regions, the construction of roads and communications. These problems and analyzes indicate further development, development of the city in the future. And this is due to the fact that from now on the following several issues are considered:

1. To take into account demographic indicators in determining the future prospects of the city through scientific study of the demographic development of the city and its forecasting
2. Modernization and diversification of urban industrial enterprises, Organization of heavy industrial enterprises using men’s labor, improvement of the sectoral and territorial composition of the industry, effective use of labor resources.
3. Organization of new types of transport and routes. Rearranging the urban transport routes, developing new routes with the preservation of existing roads: generating large traffic jams “building underground bridge for pedestrian crossing to side of the World Market” Gate took pulling the road from the eastern part of

⁹⁹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlis Senati yigirma uchinchi yalpi majlisi. <https://daryo.uz/k/2019/10/11>.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur Park to Alisher Navoi street “pulling the road that turns the market from the central gate to eastern part of The increase in the population in this volume and the increase in the number of light cars necessitates the construction of roads the placement of central street in the new residential areas under construction.

4. Using foreign experiences to give a modern urban landscape in the future. In 2019, an agreement was signed with alqusair company of Saudiya Arabia to restore Namangan city on the area to 78. In the same order, it is desirable to raise the rest of the city in stages¹⁰⁰. The main emphasis of the is on the fact that along with the old regions of the city, it is desirable to place such high objects of urban planning, as well as the territories included in the composition of the new city.

5. It is necessary to provide the population working in the social sphere with housing. The agglomerative environment manifests itself in the presence of a pendulous connection between the village and the city. Most of the population in the district goes to the city every day to work in the city. This increases the population mass. To prevent this, it is necessary to restore small towns in the districts. For example, the Chuja and Uchtepa villages of the Naryn district can be converted into a tourist town on the basis of an Axsikent monument, a Shahand village in the Naryn district.

Analysis shows that there are a number of problems in urban development. First of all, it is required to increase its industrial potential, to further improve its networks and territorial composition. for this purpose, the convenient geographical location of the city, available agricultural resources, labor resources, located around the city are full of population addresses it is necessary to carry out more work on use, construction and landscaping.

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¹⁰⁰ <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2019/10/22/namangan-city>